

PREDICTING THE FAILURE OF ORGANIC MATRIX COMPOSITES INCORPORATING THE EFFECTS OF PROCESSING

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ABSTRACT

In this work, the effects of processing on the predicted failure response of polymer matrix composites (PMCs) are investigated. Failure modeling often considers the stress-free state as the reference configuration for subsequent loading; however, this work demonstrates the effects of the residual stress-strain state, which is a result of non-uniform thermal histories combined with the evolution of anisotropic material properties during the curing process.

The analyses are performed on an angle bracket with a symmetric, 16 ply layup. The angle bracket & tooling are modeled using finite elements and subjected to the virtual cure cycle. Specifically, the thermomechanical boundary conditions as a function of time are simulated in the finite element analyses. At each increment in the finite element procedure, the material properties as a function of degree of cure are calculated using the material property models in COMPRO. Due to the temperature gradients and ply orientations, the part experiences spring-in due to the residual stresses.

The failure of the angle bracket is then predicted using discrete damage modeling methodology, and the results are compared for a case in which no residual stresses are considered and a case in which the effects of the processing cycle (i.e. residual stresses) are considered. In the latter, the non-mechanical strains and spatially varying material properties, resulting from the processing cycle, are subsequently applied to the part geometry. After equilibrating to a reference state, the part is then loaded to failure.

1 INTRODUCTION

Organic matrix composites (OMCs) represent a low cost and low weight alternative to aerospace applications that also demand high stiffness and strength. While numerous applications have replaced traditionally metallic components with OMCs, there still exist unique challenges in accurately predicting and extending the life of such components. Due to the more often more complex microstructure of OMCs as compared to metallic components, for example, additional rigor must be taken in capturing and predicting the complete history of OMC parts.

Traditional processing of organic matrix composites is performed with complex temperature and mechanical (i.e. pressure) boundary conditions (“cure cycles”) applied as a function of time. Due to the varying sizes and specifications of processing equipment and conditions, cure cycles are often defined with ranges bounding the thermal and mechanical parameters. Using these ranges, variations not only within a single autoclave but also between autoclaves can be accommodated. These variations, however, often result in different final configurations of the OMC parts. Specifically, these different thermal and mechanical histories can result in different degrees of cure, residual stresses, porosity, or microstructure morphology. Such effects often lead to variations in the ultimate strength of the composite and must be considered in the subsequent failure analyses.

Numerous efforts [1-12] have focused on developing the mathematical models to capture the complex material behavior during the cure cycle that leads to residual stresses. Early efforts [1-4], for example, considered only the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) mismatch between plies of varying orientations. Through considering only the CTE mismatch, however, the residual stress is assumed to be a function only of the final temperature and degree of cure experienced during the cure cycle and does not include additional effects such as cure shrinkage. These additional effects have been demonstrated to have an effect on the OMC residual stress state [13]. Experimental [13-18] and computational [18-21] studies have further demonstrated the impact of the cure cycle on the resulting residual stresses and failure strength [13,18].

In this paper, the methodology used to incorporate the effects of processing on the strength of OMCs will be demonstrated. Specifically, residual stresses for a nominal cure cycle will be used as the reference configuration for a failure analysis. The load-displacement response of the OMC with no residual stresses will be compared to the response with residual stresses.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Preliminaries

The focus of the analyses in this work is on a nominally 90° angle bracket with a quasi-isotropic layup. Specifically, the angle brackets consist of a 16 ply $[45/90/-45/0]_{2s}$ layup, fabricated using Cytec Engineered Materials (CEM) Cycom[®] 5320-1 resin with IM7 12K tows. The angle brackets have a nominal width of 152.4 mm (6"), a filleted bend with a radius of 0.635 mm (0.25"), and leg lengths of 88.9 mm (3.5"). The parts are fabricated on a solid steel, male tool. A schematic of the part and tool geometry is shown in Figure 1, noting that only half the width is shown due to symmetry conditions.

Upon removing the angle brackets from the tool, the deviations from the nominal 90° were measured and used as an indirect metric of the accumulated residual stresses in the brackets. In a previous experimental effort [13], the residual stresses were measured when subjecting the angle bracket to eight cure cycles that varied the gel temperature (93°C , 135°C), the temperature ramp rate ($0.3^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, $0.7^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$), and the postcure method (integrated, freestanding). In this work, a nominally 90° angle bracket will be used to demonstrate the methodology for incorporating the processing residual stresses on the damage analysis.

2.2 Process Modeling

Accurate modeling of the curing process for thermosetting organic matrix composites requires a detailed representation of the boundary conditions and the physical changes through which the OMC is evolving. As such, the method used in this work separates the process modeling into two steps – a thermo-chemical analysis and stress analysis – as shown in Figure 2. These analyses are performed in Abaqus[®] 6.14-1, using the COMPRO[®] material library add-on developed by Convergent Manufacturing Technologies, Inc. This library calculates the material properties, including the cure kinetics, thermal conductivity, specific heat, cure shrinkage, and modulus, at each integration point for the composite materials.

In the thermo-chemical step, the angle bracket is placed on the male tool. The thermal boundary conditions are applied through convective boundary conditions such that the ambient temperature is set to the programmed autoclave or oven temperature cycle. The autoclave is programmed such that

Figure 1 – Schematic of the angle bracket and tool geometry.

the part experiences the nominally desired cure cycle and the finite element convection coefficients for the outer surfaces of the part and tool are calibrated to fit the predicted temperature profiles with the experimentally-measured thermocouple data.

The temperature profile resulting from the thermo-chemical simulation, accounting for the thermal material properties as a function of the evolving degree of cure, is used as input to the second step of the cure modeling – the stress analysis step. In this step, a pressure of 1 atm is applied to the exterior surface of the part to simulate the pressure applied due to the vacuum bagging. At each time step, the temperature profile from the heat transfer step is used to calculate the current degree of cure of the composite, which is used as input to the mechanical property models (modulus, cure shrinkage coefficient, coefficient of thermal expansion, etc.). At the end of the cure cycle, the pressure and tool is removed, allowing the composite part to acquire its natural configuration.

The angle bracket was modeled using linear elements for each of the thermo-chemical and the stress analysis. Through the thickness, one element was assigned per ply. In addition, the in-plane elements each corresponded to a physical size of 1mm x 1mm. The choice of mesh refinement was significantly larger than the number of elements necessary to converge on the process modeling but provided additional locations for crack insertion in the subsequent failure analysis. At the end of the two-step simulation process, the acquired natural configuration is a bracket with an angle less than 90°.

Figure 2 – Schematic of the modeling methodology, including the sequential thermal and mechanical process modeling analyses performed with Abaqus and COMPRO and the subsequent linkage to the damage modeling performed in BSAM.

2.3 Damage Modeling

The material state of the composite laminate after cure is “handed off” to a mechanistic model within which the laminate is loaded to failure, as shown in Figure 2. In this section, an overview of the linkage between the process modeling and the mechanical performance model is provided, and then a description of the mechanical performance model is presented.

Carbon fiber reinforced PMC laminates in a typical state, as processed according to manufacturer recommended cure cycle, are relatively brittle and their deformation is well described by an elastic constituent model. As such, for a given orthotropic ply of a fully cured composite, the stress-strain relationship at each coordinate location can be written as

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \mathbf{e}_n) \quad (1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$, \mathbf{C} and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ are stress, stiffness and strain tensors respectively and \mathbf{e}_n is the tensor of nonmechanical strain. All tensors are functions of coordinate \mathbf{x} , which is omitted in Eqn. (1). For a thermoelastic material, the nonmechanical strain tensor is often simply the thermal expansion strain tensor, i.e.

$$\mathbf{e}_n = \Delta T \boldsymbol{\alpha} \quad (2)$$

where ΔT – is the temperature change and $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ is the tensor of thermal expansion coefficients. Constitutive equations (1) and (2) provide a simplistic way of evaluation of the residual processing stress by assuming that they are caused exclusively by thermal mismatch and that the elastic modulus

and thermal expansion coefficients are constant between the stress free temperature and test temperature and independent of degree of cure. For such estimates, the temperature change is set $\Delta T = \text{test temperature} - \text{stress free temperature}$. The solution of the equilibrium equations with the constitutive equations (1) - (2) provides a stress-strain state corresponding to processing residual stress and distortion. This estimate is, however, very crude and completely neglects any history dependent effects of cure as well as chemical shrinkage. The approach taken below is based on the assumption of elastic behavior (1) in the cured condition; however, the non-mechanical strain is computed based on the processing simulation results.

As described in the previous section, the processing simulation provides the stress, stiffness and strain tensors $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$, \mathbf{C} and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ as a function of degree of cure α , and temperature T at each coordinate location. These tensors are computed as a result of nonlinear multiphysics computation. It is assumed that only states with high degree of cure at which the material satisfies (1) are considered. In this case, by knowing the tensors $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$, \mathbf{C} and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ at each location \mathbf{x} , the nonmechanical strain tensor is computed from equation (1) as

$$\mathbf{e}_n(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{C}^{-1}(\mathbf{x})\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{x}) - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{x}) \quad (3)$$

Note that the nonmechanical strain computed in Eqn. (3) combined with the stiffness tensor provide complete definition of the material properties of the cured composite. Depending upon the cure history, both the stiffness tensor and the nonmechanical strain can have a different distribution. What is important is that the equilibrium stress and strain fields $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ obtained from cure simulation and the equilibrium stress/strain fields resulting from elastic solution with constitutive equations (1) and (3) will be identical under the same boundary conditions. It is assumed that no further change of stiffness or nonmechanical strain is occurring and $\alpha(\mathbf{x})$ and $T(\mathbf{x})$ will be fixed everywhere during the mechanical loading.

The apparent nonlinearity of the mechanical response under loading can be caused by matrix cracking, delamination and fiber failure initiation and propagation. This apparent nonlinearity is a result of formation of displacement discontinuities associated with cracking and delamination and not related to constitutive equations (1) - (3) in pristine material, which will hold at all times.

A discrete damage modeling (DDM) framework, in which damage modes such as matrix cracking and delamination can originate, propagate and interact at arbitrary, initially undefined locations, is used. The DDM methodology [22,23], is built on Mesh Independent Crack (MIC) technique [24]. The essence of this technique is insertion of true displacement discontinuities independently of mesh orientation to simulate matrix cracking. Multiple cracking in each ply is allowed. The minimum cracking distance is dictated by the mesh so that the cracks have to be about 5 elements apart. All plies are tied together by using cohesive interfaces which are allowed to delaminate.

A cohesive interface formulation [25] is used for both delamination and MIC propagation. The computation begins without any matrix cracks present. First, a thermal loading case is performed to account for processing residual stress. The pre-stressed composite is then incrementally loaded and, on each loading increment, the 3D failure criterion [26] is evaluated. If the criterion is exceeded for a matrix failure mode, then a matrix crack is inserted. Next the load is increased and the program enters a nonlinear iteration step at which the inserted crack(s) and/or delamination(s) are being opened. After convergence is achieved, the failure criterion is checked again for new crack insertion. This process can be coupled with progressive simulation of fiber failure and/or fiber criterion if applicable; however, this work does consider fiber failure modes. The schematic of the process is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 – Schematic of the static solution algorithm used to predict the failure of the polymer matrix composite part.

3 RESULTS

The 16 ply quasi-isotropic angle bracket was virtually subjected to a nominal cure cycle. At the end of the process model simulation, the part was removed from the tool and allowed to elastically deform to its natural configuration. After converting the residual stresses to non-mechanical strains, the angle brackets were loaded to predict damage. The loading for the angle brackets, as shown in Figure 4, was adapted from the loading conducted in curved beam strength (CBS) tests. Specifically, a downward displacement was applied on the top surface of the bracket while supports on the bottom of the bracket were used to prevent vertical displacement. The displacements were applied approximately 75 mm apart (3 in.), and the lower supports were approximately 100 mm apart.

Figure 4 – Schematic of applied displacements and boundary conditions for damage predictions of angle brackets.

The preliminary load-displacement curves and crack patterns for the two cases (with and without residual stresses) are shown in Figure 5 and Figure 6, respectively. It is observed that accounting for the residual stresses results in a clear deviation in the load-displacement curve and the number of cracks predicted in the angle bracket; however, efforts are ongoing to increase the resolution and number of data points for both the initial loading of the brackets and the extent of loading for the case with no residual stresses to provide a more complete comparison of the mechanical path.

Figure 5 – Load-displacement response a 90° angle bracket comparing the effects of considering the processing residual stresses. The bracket with residual stresses included experiences a deviation from the load-displacement response of the bracket with no residual stresses included.

Figure 6 – Crack contours for the angle brackets when (a) residual stresses are considered compared to (b) the case with no residual stresses.

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a methodology to incorporate the effects of processing on the residual stresses and subsequent failure predictions of organic matrix composites were presented. Specifically, the effects were preliminarily demonstrated on a 16 ply angle bracket consisting of a quasi-isotropic [-45/90/-45/0]_{2s} layup. The processing of the angle brackets was simulated using Abaqus and COMPRO, and the resulting spatially-varying material properties and residual stresses were used as input to a discrete damage modeling framework.

The angle brackets were then loaded in a 4-point bend configuration adapted from a curved beam strength test, and the load-displacement response and damage was compared to the case in which the cure cycle and residual stress state was not considered. It was predicted that the residual processing stresses cause a deviation in the failure.

This work establishes an essential link to increasing the fidelity of damage modeling for polymer matrix composites by considering the processing history of the part. Additional efforts are ongoing to refine and validate the computational predictions against actual residual stress and curved beam strength experimental data. Ongoing and future efforts are also focused at quantifying the error in the computational predictions, including the effects of machining, and including the effects of the processing cycle on the formation of voids and defects, which further affect the strength of the PMCs.

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